

Bridging Present and Future: 5G and Bidirectional Charging for Scalable Urban Mobility Solutions

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Abstract: This paper presents a fifth-generation (5G)-enabled bidirectional charging testbed that bridges campus experimentation and an urban pilot deployment in Dresden’s Ostra district (2×50 kW chargers, 3 electric vehicles (EVs), private 5G network). We detail the transition from a direct communication setup to a layered architecture integrating an urban mobility and energy platform (IMEP) for data aggregation and a cloud-ready control and optimisation service (COS) for real-time scheduling, addressing urban scalability challenges such as data flow orchestration, protocol integration, and grid interaction. At the current scale, the control traffic could be handled by wired or long-term evolution (LTE) connections; our use of a private 5G network is therefore a strategic choice to validate an architecture intended to scale to scenarios with hundreds of EVs and dozens of chargers coordinated via cloud-based control. We define end-to-end control latency below 15 ms as a key design objective for vehicle-to-grid (V2G) and vehicle-to-building (V2B) operations and identify practical integration constraints in charger interfaces and state-of-charge reporting that the pilot setup must address. The pilot design also reflects the “faraway water” adoption barrier, where stakeholders hesitate to invest in bidirectional charging absent clear incentives and ecosystem maturity. Building on these insights, we identify critical planning gaps (regulatory standardisation, infrastructure investment) and outline pathways toward city-wide deployment across Dresden’s 76 planned mobility hubs, providing urban planners and infrastructure developers with a blueprint and evaluation plan for scalable smart city energy systems.

1 INTRODUCTION

Urban environments are at the forefront of the global transition toward sustainability, with smart cities increasingly leveraging digital and energy technologies to address challenges in mobility and energy systems [Sharma and Kanwal, 2023]. The European Green Deal’s target of reducing transport-related emissions by 90% by 2050 underscores the urgency of integrating low-carbon solutions into urban infrastructure [European Commission, 2023]. Electric vehicles (EVs) play a central role in this transition; however, large-scale EV adoption introduces significant challenges for power grids, including increased peak demand and reduced system stability. Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) technology mitigates these challenges by enabling bidirectional power exchange between EVs and the grid, effectively transforming EVs into distributed energy storage resources that

support grid stabilisation and renewable energy integration [Casella et al., 2022, Rao et al., 2025]. We use Vehicle-to-Building (V2B) to denote bidirectional exchanges at the building level, and reserve Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) as an umbrella term; whenever we discuss concrete services or implementations, we refer explicitly to V2G or V2B. Smart city infrastructure such as intelligent street lighting, often used as a foundational platform for urban energy efficiency [Petrìtoli et al., 2019], illustrates how existing “street-level” assets can be leveraged for EU green development. In a similar spirit, this work treats charging infrastructure and mobility hubs as critical building blocks for integrating EVs into smart city energy systems.

While prior work has demonstrated the potential of optimised EV charging through simulation studies, including work conducted in Dresden’s Ostra district [Wang et al., 2025a], the practical de-

ployment of V2G systems presents additional challenges. These include scalability constraints, regulatory barriers, and the need for reliable, low-latency, and secure communication between EVs, charging infrastructure, and energy management platforms. Fifth-generation (5G) mobile networks are well positioned to address these requirements by enabling real-time data exchange and dynamic energy management across heterogeneous urban systems. At the current pilot scale, the control traffic could be handled by wired or LTE connectivity; our choice of a private 5G network is therefore a strategic design decision to validate an architecture intended to scale to hundreds of EVs and dozens of chargers coordinated via cloud-based control.

A preliminary version of the system architecture, including the layered communication and functional design (Figs. 3 and 5), was introduced in [Wang et al., 2025b]. Building on this foundation, the present work extends the architecture toward a real-world pilot deployment in Dresden’s Ostra district, addressing scalability aspects and the so-called “faraway water” challenge through coordinated system design and data flow management. As part of the Mobilities for EU project [Mobilities for EU Consortium, 2024], this paper focuses on smart charging and bidirectional charging as key enablers for integrating EVs into urban energy systems.

The proposed system is structured into two tightly coupled layers: a network layer and a functional layer. The network layer comprises the data network, user plane function (UPF), local edge computing, radio access network (RAN), and user equipment (UE), providing reliable and low-latency connectivity. The functional layer integrates the Integrated Mobility and Energy Platform (IMEP) for data aggregation and coordination, along with the Charging Optimization System (COS) for real-time charging and discharging decisions.

The pilot setup integrates two bidirectional charging stations, a photovoltaic-equipped building, and up to three EVs, coordinated via a private 5G network. This configuration is designed to demonstrate the feasibility of transitioning from a controlled testbed to an urban pilot and to expose integration issues that will be critical at larger scales. It highlights key challenges related to data flow orchestration, protocol integration, and grid interaction, while illustrating the potential of bidirectional charging to enhance grid flexibility and support sustainable urban energy systems.

Compared to our earlier Ostra district simulations, which analysed V2G benefits at district scale [Wang et al., 2025a], this paper contributes: (i) an implemented end-to-end architecture connecting driver

app, backend optimiser, chargers, and building via a private 5G network; (ii) a detailed description of the data flows and communication protocols required for real-world operation; and (iii) architectural lessons and scalability considerations for expanding from a small pilot to scenarios with on the order of 200 EVs and 50 chargers in multiple sites, including a concrete evaluation plan for upcoming pilot operation.

2 Project Overview: From Campus to City

V2X technology enhances grid stability and supports sustainable urban mobility by enabling EVs to function as mobile energy storage units [Wang et al., 2024a]. This creates business opportunities such as EV owners participating in demand response programmes, providing ancillary grid services, and earning revenue by selling stored energy during peak demand, as well as enabling peer-to-peer energy trading [Rao et al., 2025]. In the remainder of this paper, we focus on concrete V2G and V2B implementations within this broader V2X context.

Our research journey progressed from theoretical concepts through a campus testbed to an urban pilot in Dresden’s Ostra district, bridging academic research and real-world implementation. A preliminary version of the communication interface between EVs, charging infrastructure, and the control optimiser, including core 5G network and functional layers, was presented in [Wang et al., 2025b]. This paper extends that foundation with full pilot integration, IMEP-coordinated data flows, and scalability analysis toward city-wide deployment.

The campus testbed validated basic bidirectional charging functionalities, while the Ostra pilot introduces urban complexity. The pilot incorporates two 50 kW rapid charging stations with dual-port capability (CCS/CHAdeMO compatible) for simultaneous EV charging, integrated with a PV-equipped building as a distributed energy resource, and up to three 75 kWh EVs. Table 1 outlines the pilot’s initial scope versus Dresden’s city-wide scaling targets. These components are managed through IMEP and a private 5G network (3.9 GHz band, 100 MHz bandwidth, < 15 ms target latency), enabling an initial evaluation of smart charging and V2G/V2B strategies in a realistic urban context and preparing the architecture for scenarios with substantially more chargers and EVs.

Charging station locations align with prior traffic simulations [Wang et al., 2025a], ensuring high fidelity between simulated and physical deployments. This flexible design addresses real-world challenges

Table 1: Ostra Pilot vs. City-Scale Requirements

Aspect	Current vs. Target
Chargers	2 (50 kW) → 152 hubs
EVs	3 (75 kWh) → 10,000+
Network	Private 5G → City-wide 5G
Data Sources	Weather+PV → +Traffic+Grid
Coverage	1 district → City-wide

including grid integration, user behaviour, and regulatory compliance, while providing insights for scaling V2G and V2B solutions across smart cities.

3 System Architecture and Implementation

3.1 Current System Architecture: Campus Testbed

Figure 1 illustrates the current campus testbed at TU Dresden, representing a simplified bidirectional charging system. It consists of two charging stations directly connected to the COS, enabling proof-of-concept testing of bidirectional charging operations.

Figure 1: Campus testbed architecture with direct COS-station communication.

Key components are:

- Two bidirectional charging stations.
- COS implementing a rule-based algorithm for charging and discharging, considering vehicle state-of-charge (SoC), user preferences, and simulated energy prices.
- Direct communication links between COS and the stations over a local network.

While suitable for small-scale testing, the campus testbed is limited in scope and complexity. Its direct communication model does not incorporate external data sources (e.g., weather forecasts, energy prices)

or advanced networking technologies, and it cannot emulate urban conditions such as grid fluctuations or large numbers of EVs [Anany et al., 2024, Rao et al., 2025]. Nevertheless, it provides a foundation for developing and validating bidirectional charging algorithms before scaling to urban environments.

3.2 Urban Implementation in Dresden’s Ostra District

Building upon the campus testbed, the implementation in Dresden’s Ostra district (Fig. 2) demonstrates how the architecture is adapted for a scalable urban deployment. The system integrates two bidirectional charging stations, up to three EVs, and a building equipped with a photovoltaic (PV) system to provide local renewable energy.

Figure 2: Scalable urban pilot architecture: IMEP + COS + 5G + PV building (Dresden Ostra).

Scalability is achieved through the Integrated Mobility and Energy Platform (IMEP), which coordinates EVs, charging stations, and the power grid. IMEP aggregates diverse data sources, including weather forecasts, energy prices, building consumption and PV generation, and EV charging requests, to generate optimized charging plans. A private 5G network (3.9 GHz, 100 MHz bandwidth, < 15 ms target latency) provides wide-area, low-latency communication for real-time control of mobile assets; at the current scale, similar functionality could be realized with wired or LTE connectivity, but 5G is adopted to validate an architecture designed for future expansion to many EVs and chargers. The system’s modular design allows new charging stations and EVs to be added without changing the core control logic, and it incorporates Building Integrated Vehicle Energy Solutions (BIVES) and Resilient Energy Storage and Backup (RESB) concepts to enhance energy management and resilience [Wang et al., 2024a].

3.3 Network and Functional Layers

Figure 3 illustrates the 5G network and functional layers. The network layer includes the data network, user plane function, local edge computing, radio access network, and user equipment. The functional layer consists of IMEP for data aggregation and coordination, COS for local charging control and optimization, and EV wall boxes/buildings as user equipment. This layered design separates communication from control, supporting secure, efficient, and scalable bidirectional charging operations.

Figure 3: 5G network and functional layer overview. Adapted from [Wang et al., 2025b].

3.4 Data Flow and Communication

The urban system's data flow is structured to integrate EVs, charging stations, and external sources while ensuring scalability and security. The layered architecture (Fig. 3) and urban system overview (Fig. 5) were first introduced in [Wang et al., 2025b]; here we focus on their realisation in the Ostra context. The overall data flow begins with EVs sending charging requests to IMEP, which integrates external sources (weather forecasts, energy prices) and building energy data, generates charging plans, and distributes them via 5G and wired connections.

The communication stack uses industry-standard protocols. ISO 15118-20 standardises EV–charging-station interactions [Santos et al., 2024], MQTT enables lightweight messaging between mobile devices and IMEP [Hillar, 2017], and OCPP 2.0.1 manages charging stations [Nguyen, 2023]. Protocol selection balances real-time requirements and security, with end-to-end encryption ensuring data privacy [Rao et al., 2025].

Campus testbed data flow. In the campus setup, COS communicates directly with the charging stations over a local network. Charging data (arrival/departure times, SoC) is exchanged in JSON format, for example:

```
{
```

```
  "ev_id": "EV001",
  "arrival_time": "202501010800",
  "departure_time": "202501011700",
  "current_soc": 0.3,
  "target_soc": 0.8
}
```

This simple setup lacks integration of external data (weather, prices), which is essential for urban-scale optimization.

Urban implementation data flow. The pilot introduces comprehensive data flows (Fig. 4):

1. **Charging requests:** EVs transmit encrypted data (arrival/departure times, battery capacity, SoC targets, minimum discharge level) to IMEP via MQTT over 5G (Fig. 4a).
2. **External data:** Weather forecasts (e.g., temperature, irradiance, precipitation) and energy prices are integrated into IMEP (Fig. 4b).
3. **Building data:** Real-time PV generation and load data feed the charging logic (Fig. 4c).
4. **Charging plans:** IMEP optimisation results are distributed via 5G and OCPP to stations/EVs (Fig. 4d).

Building PV and load data drive renewable prioritisation through predictive algorithms matching EV schedules to local generation, minimising grid reliance and supporting bidirectional charging and real-time grid response [Wang et al., 2024b].

3.5 Transition from Direct Communication to 5G and IMEP Platform

Figure 5 illustrates the comprehensive system architecture for the urban implementation of bidirectional charging. The transition from a direct communication model to one leveraging 5G and a central IMEP introduces several advanced capabilities:

- **Enhanced scalability:** The architecture supports simultaneous communication with many EVs and charging stations across a larger area, and can be extended to additional sites without changing the field devices. This marks a significant improvement over the campus testbed, which was limited to direct connections between COS and individual stations.
- **Real-time optimisation:** Low control-plane latency enables frequent updates to charging schedules based on grid conditions and vehicle needs. For example, the system can adjust charging rates in response to grid constraints or updated SoC estimates, ensuring vehicles reach their target SoC

Figure 4: Data flows across the 5G+IMEP urban architecture: inputs (a–c) feed the IMEP optimisation engine; output (d) is distributed via OCPP/MQTT to enable real-time V2G/V2B coordination.

Figure 5: Comprehensive urban bidirectional charging system with 5G+IMEP. Adapted from [Wang et al., 2025b].

before departure while contributing to grid flexibility.

- **Advanced services:** IMEP enables advanced services such as dynamic pricing, demand response, and peer-to-peer energy trading, which are not feasible with the direct communication model used in the campus testbed. These features require central coordination and data processing capabilities, coupled with reliable communication provided by the underlying network.

4 Challenges and Scalability Pathways

4.1 Technical Challenges

While this architecture prepares the system for scalability, it also introduces significant technical chal-

lenges. As the system scales, it must efficiently process and securely manage increasing amounts of data from multiple EVs, charging stations, and external sources [Zafar et al., 2023, Metere et al., 2021]. Implementing secure communication protocols such as ISO 15118 with Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) can help protect against unauthorised access and data tampering [Vaidya et al., 2014].

Edge computing can help manage traffic flowing to virtual machines and container-based applications deployed in edge data centres, ensuring continuous service and low-latency responses. Balancing computational loads by determining the optimal distribution of processes between edge devices (e.g., charging stations) and cloud platforms is essential to optimise response times and network efficiency [Kumar et al., 2020, Huang et al., 2015].

A significant concern is load balancing in unbalanced distribution grids. As demonstrated by Weckx and Driesen, adapting EV chargers and PV inverters for load balancing can significantly improve grid conditions, including voltage levels and system losses [Weckx and Driesen, 2015]. However, this requires careful integration of V2G technology into vehicles and the power market, including smart meters for monitoring and managing energy flow and robust grid management with improved control technologies to handle increasing demand while maintaining grid stability [Demuth et al., 2024].

The expansion of smart-charging infrastructure presents additional challenges: addressing battery degradation due to increased charging cycles in bidirectional charging is essential for long-term viability [Demuth et al., 2024]. Tackling these technical challenges is crucial for scaling bidirectional charging systems from individual buildings to city-wide implementations and aligning them with broader smart city and energy system goals.

4.2 Implementation Challenges: Bridging the Gap Between Vision and Reality

Scaling up bidirectional charging systems presents significant implementation challenges, demanding a holistic approach that addresses technical, economic, and social considerations.

Regulatory and standardisation hurdles. A primary obstacle is the lack of harmonised technical standards and operational rules across regions. This patchwork of regulations hinders efficient energy pricing and limits compatibility between EVs and charging infrastructure [Agency, 2023, Demuth et al., 2024]. Clear policies governing battery use in bidirectional charging and standardised charging plugs are essential to overcome these limitations.

Infrastructure investment and availability. Expanding charging infrastructure and integrating bidirectional capabilities into EVs, charging stations, and grid management systems requires substantial investment. The high cost of DC fast chargers, crucial for high-power bidirectional charging, further exacerbates this challenge. The limited availability of V2G-capable vehicles restricts widespread adoption, necessitating increased production and affordability of compatible EVs [Visakh and Manickavasagam Parvathy, 2022, Demuth et al., 2024].

The “faraway water” problem. Beyond technical and economic hurdles, a key challenge lies in aligning the long-term vision of V2G with the immediate needs of potential adopters. In discussions with the facility manager in Dresden’s Ostra district, initial enthusiasm about peak shaving and demand response benefits faded once it became clear that these benefits depend on a mature V2G ecosystem with many EVs and charging stations, a future scenario that does not solve current energy challenges. This “faraway water cannot quench the present fire” dynamic highlights a fundamental obstacle: demonstrating immediate value to encourage early adoption.

This challenge underscores the need for collaboration between researchers, urban planners, and city planning teams. Technical, regulatory, and policy hurdles can be addressed in research projects, but the successful implementation of V2G ultimately relies on aligning future-oriented system designs with the present needs of stakeholders and providing tangible, near-term value.

4.3 Market Readiness and Adoption

The market readiness and adoption of bidirectional charging face several challenges despite its potential

benefits. As identified in our previous work, implementing V2G/V2B technology in urban settings encounters regulatory and business-model hurdles, including the need for standardised protocols, clear regulatory frameworks for energy trading, and viable business models that incentivise EV owners to participate in grid services [Wang et al., 2024a]. A significant barrier to customer participation is current taxation schemes that penalise feeding energy from EV batteries back into the grid. Establishing consumer-focused incentives from an electricity system perspective is crucial for widespread adoption. Experts project that V2G technology will be widely deployed in developed countries within 5–10 years, allowing time for necessary infrastructure development and consumer education [Demuth et al., 2024].

Consumer adoption challenges remain substantial. Concerns about losing control over charging and potential limitations on vehicle usage deter many potential users. Financial incentives therefore play a crucial role. Governments, utilities, and stakeholders should consider offering rewards, tax credits, or preferential electricity rates to encourage participation in bidirectional charging programmes [Demuth et al., 2024]. Addressing these issues will be crucial in bridging the gap between available technology and market preparedness.

4.4 Scalability Pathways: From Pilot to City-wide Impact

Our engagement with Dresden stakeholders underscores the difficulty of aligning V2G’s transformative potential with immediate adopter needs. Initial enthusiasm often fades when stakeholders realise that benefits depend on a mature EV ecosystem—a microcosm of early adoption barriers. Effective strategies must therefore demonstrate near-term value tailored to specific needs while keeping the long-term vision.

The 5G-enabled architecture provides a robust foundation for scaling from the Ostra pilot (Table 1) toward Dresden’s 76 MOBIpunkte mobility hubs [Landeshauptstadt Dresden, 2018]. It can support growing EV fleets and more complex bidirectional scenarios, enhancing grid stability, renewable integration, and emissions reduction [Wang et al., 2024a, Wang et al., 2024b]. At the current small scale, similar functionality could be provided by wired or LTE connectivity, but the chosen architecture anticipates the requirements of city-wide deployment.

City-wide scaling will require infrastructure upgrades (smart stations, advanced grid management for EV variability) coordinated with broader smart city initiatives. Key technical challenges include

data-volume management, secure transmission, and edge–cloud load balancing, which demand advanced analytics, load prediction algorithms, and robust cybersecurity [Wang et al., 2024b].

Future research priorities include:

- Optimising 5G configurations for EV-related data streams and scalable energy-management algorithms.
- Developing supportive regulatory frameworks, standards, and collaboration mechanisms between automakers, utilities, and policymakers.
- Designing user-centric interfaces (apps and dashboards) that make real-time value and control transparent for users.
- Exploring flexible business models (e.g., dynamic tariffs, shared savings) that help bridge the “far-away water” gap [Demuth et al., 2024].

5 Conclusion

This paper presented a scalable 5G-enabled bidirectional charging architecture for Dresden’s Ostra district, extending our prior simulation and communication work [Wang et al., 2025a, Wang et al., 2025b]. It translates district-level optimisation results into a concrete system design with two bidirectional chargers, a PV-equipped building, and a private 5G network, and details how driver apps, IMEP, COS, and charging stations are interconnected through standardised protocols and layered communication.

Our contributions are threefold: a detailed technical architecture and data-flow description for 5G-enabled V2G/V2B systems, an analysis of urban scaling challenges including the “faraway water” adoption barrier, and a set of city-scale research directions and evaluation metrics. At the current small scale, the control traffic could be handled by wired or LTE connectivity; the use of private 5G is a strategic choice to validate an architecture designed to scale to scenarios with hundreds of EVs and dozens of chargers coordinated via cloud-based control.

The Ostra pilot design shows how 5G+IMEP can support real-time coordination of bidirectional charging, but also highlights regulatory lags, infrastructure needs, and challenges in demonstrating immediate value to local stakeholders. Scaling to Dresden’s 76 MOBIpunkte hubs [Landeshauptstadt Dresden, 2018] will require coordinated policy (e.g., supportive taxation and V2G tariffs), planning (integration with smart city strategies), and technology (user-centric interfaces and interoperable devices).

As part of the Mobilities for EU project, this work provides a blueprint that bridges campus testbeds and urban pilots, positioning EVs as dynamic grid assets for sustainable urban mobility. Future work will include completing the installation and commissioning of the Ostra pilot, collecting operational data using defined KPIs, comparing measured performance with simulation assumptions, and developing barrier-removal business models that can further support pilot-to-practice deployment at city scale.

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REFERENCES

- Agency, I. E. (2023). Unlocking smart grid opportunities in emerging markets and developing economies. Accessed: 2024-07-01.
- Anany, M. G., ElDesouky, A. A., and Salem, A. A. (2024). Real-time v2g simulator for grid system frequency and voltage regulation with fault ride-through capabilities. *Electric Power Systems Research*, 234:110561.
- Casella, V., Fernandez Valderrama, D., Ferro, G., Minciardi, R., Paolucci, M., Parodi, L., and Robba, M. (2022). Towards the integration of sustainable transportation and smart grids: A review on electric vehicles’ management. *Energies*, 15(11).
- Demuth, J. L., Buberger, J., Huber, A., Behrens, E., Kuder, M., and Weyh, T. (2024). Unveiling the power of data in bidirectional charging: A qualitative stakeholder approach exploring the potential and challenges of v2g. *Green Energy and Intelligent Transportation*, 3(6):100225.
- European Commission (2023). Annual activity report 2023. Report, Directorate General for Mobility and Trans-

- port (DG MOVE), Brussels, Belgium. European Commission transport and mobility report.
- Hillar, G. C. (2017). *MQTT Essentials-A lightweight IoT protocol*. Packt Publishing Ltd.
- Huang, Q., Jia, Q.-S., Qiu, Z., Guan, X., and Deconinck, G. (2015). Matching ev charging load with uncertain wind: A simulation-based policy improvement approach. *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, 6(3):1425–1433.
- Kumar, N., Dhand, T., Jindal, A., Aujla, G. S., Cao, H., and Yang, L. (2020). An edge-fog computing framework for cloud of things in vehicle to grid environment. In *2020 IEEE 21st International Symposium on "A World of Wireless, Mobile and Multimedia Networks" (WoWMoM)*, pages 354–359. IEEE.
- Landeshauptstadt Dresden (2018). Elektromobilität in Dresden – Potenzialstudie. Technical report, TU Dresden, Lehrstuhl für Verkehrsökologie, Dresden, Germany.
- Metere, R., Neaimeh, M., Morisset, C., Maple, C., Bellekens, X., and Czekster, R. M. (2021). Securing the electric vehicle charging infrastructure. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2105.02905*.
- Mobilities for EU Consortium (2024). Mobilities for EU. <https://mobilities-for.eu/>.
- Nguyen, Q. H. (2023). *Evaluation and development of the bridging application between ISO 15118 and OCPP 2.0.1 protocols*. PhD thesis, Rheinland-Pfälzische Technische Universität Kaiserslautern-Landau.
- Petriloti, E., Leccese, F., Pizzuti, S., and Pieroni, F. (2019). Smart lighting as basic building block of smart city: An energy performance comparative case study. *Measurement*, 136:466–477.
- Rao, S. P., Olusegun, T. S., Ranganathan, P., Kose, U., and Goveas, N. (2025). Vehicle-to-grid technology: Opportunities, challenges, and future prospects for sustainable transportation. *Journal of Energy Storage*, 110:114927.
- Santos, J. B., Francisco, A. M., Cabrita, C., Monteiro, J., Pacheco, A., and Cardoso, P. J. (2024). Development and implementation of a smart charging system for electric vehicles based on the iso 15118 standard. *Energies*, 17(12):3045.
- Sharma, H. and Kanwal, N. (2023). Smart cities: A worldwide journey into intelligent urbanism and state-of-the-art technologies. *Scientific and Technical Information Processing*, 50(4):328–355.
- Vaidya, B., Makrakis, D., and Mouftah, H. (2014). Effective public key infrastructure for vehicle-to-grid network. In *Proceedings of the fourth ACM international symposium on Development and analysis of intelligent vehicular networks and applications*, pages 95–101.
- Visakh, A. and Manickavasagam Parvathy, S. (2022). Energy-cost minimization with dynamic smart charging of electric vehicles and the analysis of its impact on distribution-system operation. *Electrical Engineering*, 104(5):2805–2817.
- Wang, S., Cabrera, J. A., and Fitzek, F. H. P. (2024a). Bidirectional charging use cases: Innovations in e-mobility and power-grid flexibility. In *IEEE International Smart Cities Conference (ISC2)*, pages 1–6, Pattaya, Thailand.
- Wang, S., Haider, S. I., Shen, S., Motazedian, F., Radeke, R., and Fitzek, F. H. P. (2025a). Simulation architecture for electric vehicle charging optimization in dresden's ostra district. In *International Conference on Smart Cities and Green ICT Systems (SMART-GREENS)*, page 56–65.
- Wang, S., Lehmann, C., Radeke, R., and Fitzek, F. H. P. (2024b). Enabling sustainable urban mobility: The role of 5g communication in the mobilities for eu project. In *IEEE International Smart Cities Conference (ISC2)*, pages 1–6, Pattaya, Thailand.
- Wang, S., Sain, A., Lehmann, C., Shen, S., Habeeb, R., and Fitzek, F. H. P. (2025b). Enabling intelligent bidirectional charging: A real-world communication interface between electric vehicles, charging infrastructure, and a control optimizer. In *E-Mobility Power System Integration Symposium*, page 8, Berlin, Germany.
- Weckx, S. and Driesen, J. (2015). Load balancing with ev chargers and pv inverters in unbalanced distribution grids. *IEEE transactions on Sustainable Energy*, 6(2):635–643.
- Zafar, S., Blavette, A., Camilleri, G., Ahmed, H. B., and Agbodjan, J.-J. P. (2023). Decentralized optimal management of a large-scale ev fleet: optimality and computational complexity comparison between an adaptive mas and milp. *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, 147:108861.